

Experimental

2-Isopropyl-5-methylphenoxyacetylhydrazide: A mixture of 2-isopropyl-5-methylphenoxyacetate (0.01 mol) in methanol (10 ml) and hydrazine hydrate (80%; 0.01 mol) was refluxed on a waterbath for 3 h. The product was isolated and crystallised from hot water, (76%), m.p. 78° (Found: C, 64.4; H, 8.00; N, 12.58. $C_{15}H_{18}O_2N_2$ calcd. for: C, 64.80; H, 8.11; N, 12.61%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 300 (NH asym.), 3 200 (NH sym.), 1 680 (C=C) and 1 250 cm^{-1} (C-O-C)⁴.

2-Amino-5-(2'-isopropyl-5'-methylphenoxy-methyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole: A mixture of 2-isopropyl-5-methylphenoxyacetylhydrazide (0.01 mol) was refluxed on a water-bath at 60° for 1.5 h and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (72%), m.p. 155° (Found: C, 62.95; H, 6.48; N, 12.65. $C_{15}H_{17}O_2N_3$ calcd. for: C, 63.15; H, 6.88; N, 12.95%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 150 (NH), 1 660 (C=N) and 1 160 cm^{-1} (C-O-C ether linkage)⁴.

2-Benzoylamino-5-(2'-isopropyl-5'-methylphenoxy-methyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazoles: A mixture of 2-amino-5-(2'-isopropyl-5'-methylphenoxy-methyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (0.01 mol) and benzoylchloride (0.01 mol) was condensed in the presence of pyridine (2.3 ml) at 80° in a water-bath for 1 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (72%), m.p. 144° (Found: C, 68.30; H, 5.94; N, 11.94. $C_{20}H_{21}O_2N_3$ calcd. for: C, 68.37; H, 5.98; N, 11.96%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 160 (NH), 1 730 (C=O), 1 670 (C=N) and 1 160 cm^{-1} (C-O-C); δ (DMSO d_6) 1.08 (6H, d, $(CH_3)_2CH$), 2.15 (3H, s, $ArCH_3$), 2.80–3.70 (1H, m, $(CH_3)_2CH$), 4.55 (2H, s, $ArOCH_2$) and 6.50–7.10 (m, ArH).

Similarly, other substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles were prepared (Table 1).

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Studies on 1,3,4-Oxadiazoles. Part-X. Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of 2-Aryl-5-p-phenylsulphophenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles

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2,5-Disubstituted-1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives have been found to possess a wide spectrum of biological properties¹. The present communication deals with the preparation of some 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives (4) with an intention to get better therapeutic agents.

p-Carbomethoxydiphenyl sulphone (2) was esterified with absolute methanol and condensed with hydrazine hydrate to get *p*-hydrazinocarbonyldiphenyl sulphone (3). Hydrazide on condensation with different aromatic acids in presence of phosphorous oxychloride gave the 2-aryl-5-*p*-phenylsulphophenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (4). The structures of the compounds (Table 1) were based on their

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 4

Sl. no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
1.	Phenyl	175	77	$C_{20}H_{14}N_2O_2S$
2.	3-Tolyl	189	69	$C_{21}H_{16}N_2O_2S$
3.	4-Tolyl	216	74	$C_{21}H_{16}N_2O_2S$
4.	2-Chlorophenyl	183	72	$C_{20}H_{13}ClN_2O_2S$
5.	3-Chlorophenyl	163	68	$C_{20}H_{13}ClN_2O_2S$
6.	4-Chlorophenyl	216	82	$C_{20}H_{13}ClN_2O_2S$
7.	2-Aminophenyl	113	58	$C_{20}H_{14}N_4O_2S$
8.	3-Aminophenyl	196	52	$C_{20}H_{14}N_4O_2S$
9.	4-Aminophenyl	190	62	$C_{20}H_{14}N_4O_2S$
10.	2-Nitrophenyl	186	79	$C_{20}H_{13}N_3O_4S$
11.	3-Nitrophenyl	159	80	$C_{20}H_{13}N_3O_4S$
12.	4-Nitrophenyl	243	84	$C_{20}H_{13}N_3O_4S$
13.	2-Hydroxyphenyl	256	72	$C_{20}H_{14}N_2O_4S$
14.	3-Hydroxyphenyl	193	68	$C_{20}H_{14}N_2O_4S$
15.	4-Hydroxyphenyl	298	79	$C_{20}H_{14}N_2O_4S$
16.	2,4-Dihydroxyphenyl	203	68	$C_{20}H_{14}N_2O_6S$
17.	2,6-Dihydroxyphenyl	226	58	$C_{20}H_{14}N_2O_6S$
18.	3,5-Dihydroxyphenyl	214	61	$C_{20}H_{14}N_2O_6S$
19.	3,4,5-Trihydroxyphenyl	138	66	$C_{20}H_{14}N_2O_7S$
20.	1-Hydroxy-2-naphthyl	282	72	$C_{21}H_{16}N_2O_3S$
21.	2-Hydroxy-3-naphthyl	290	78	$C_{21}H_{16}N_2O_3S$
22.	2-Methoxyphenyl	143	71	$C_{21}H_{18}N_2O_3S$
23.	2,3-Dimethoxyphenyl	187	76	$C_{22}H_{20}N_2O_4S$
24.	2-Acetyloxyphenyl	177	67	$C_{22}H_{18}N_2O_5S$
25.	Benzoylaminoethyl	293	64	$C_{23}H_{17}N_2O_3S$
26.	Benzyl	104	58	$C_{23}H_{19}N_2O_2S$
27.	1-Methylphenyl	135	52	$C_{23}H_{19}N_2O_2S$
28.	2-Phenethyl	155	59	$C_{23}H_{19}N_2O_2S$
29.	3-Pyridyl	228	62	$C_{19}H_{13}N_3O_2S$
30.	4-Pyridyl	214	63	$C_{19}H_{13}N_3O_2S$
31.	4-Bromophenyl	196	72	$C_{20}H_{13}BrN_2O_2S$

elemental, ir, pmr and mass spectral data. The products were screened for their antimicrobial activity.

Antimicrobial activity: The antimicrobial screening of oxadiazole derivatives was carried out using cup-plate method⁸ at a concentration of 50 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ using gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus*, *S. citreus*, gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli*, *Marcasane serratia* and fungi *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, *Aspergillus niger*.

The results showed that most of the compounds were moderately active (10–20 mm zone of inhibition) against different strains of bacteria and fungi. Maximum activity was observed in 2,5-disubstituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (4) when R = 2-methoxyphenyl and 4-bromophenyl against *A. niger*, when R = 3-tolyl against *S. cerevisiae*, when R = 4-tolyl and 4-nitrophenyl against *M. serratia*. The activity is not comparable with the known antibiotic like chloromycetin and penicillin under similar condition.

Experimental

Melting points of the compounds were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The structure of the compounds have been established on the basis of their elemental and spectral data. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu DR-1, 435-IR spectrophotometer, pmr spectra on XL-100A, 100.1 MHz spectrometer using TMS as internal reference standard, and mass spectra were scanned on a Finnigan MAT 1020B quadrupole spectrometer at 70 eV.

p-Carboxydiphenyl sulphone (2): A mixture of p-carboxydiphenyl sulphone (64.52 g, 0.246 mol), absolute methanol (101 ml, 2.5 mol) and concentrated sulphuric acid (5 g, 2.7 ml) was refluxed for 5 h. The excess methanol was then distilled off and the residue poured onto crushed ice. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (56.6 g, 83.3%), m.p. 146° (Found: S, 11.66. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4\text{S}$ requires: S, 11.60%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 155, 1 320

(S=O asym. and sym., respectively), 1 725 (C=O) and 2 940 cm^{-1} (CH_2 sym.); δ (DMSO- d_6) 3.94 (3H, s, OOCCH_3) and 8.22–7.54 (9H, m, ArH); m/z (rel. intensity%) 276 (M^+ , 13) 245 (10), 183(23), 125 (100) and 77(24).

p-Hydrazinocarbonyldiphenyl sulphone (3): An aqueous solution of hydrazine hydrate (5 ml, 80%) was added to a suspension of p-carboxydiphenyl sulphone (5.52 g, 0.02 mol) in ethanol (15 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 6 h and then cooled to room temperature and poured into ice-water. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (4.52 g, 82%), m.p. 199° (lit.⁸ 199°) (Found: N, 10.19. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{S}$ requires: N, 10.14%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 155, 1 290 (S=O asym. and sym., respectively), 1 670 (C=O) and 3 300 cm^{-1} (NH or NH_2); δ (DMSO- d_6) 4.6 (2H, s, NHNH_2), 8.2–7.5 (9H, m, ArH) and 10.06 (1H, s, CONH); m/z (rel. intensity%) 276 (M^+ , 48) 245 (100), 152 (23), 141 (22), 125 (61) and 77 (20).

2-Aryl-5-p-phenylsulphophenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4): A mixture of 3 (2.76 g, 0.01 mol), benzoic acid (1.22 g, 0.01 mol) and phosphorous oxychloride (2.5 ml) was refluxed for 6 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from dioxane–DMF (3 : 1) solvent, (2.78 g, 77%), m.p. 175° (Found: C, 66.22; H, 3.90; N, 7.68. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{S}$ requires: C, 66.27; H, 3.89; N, 7.73%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 155, 1 320 (S=O asym. and sym., respectively), 1 105 and 1 670 cm^{-1} (=COC= and C=N, respectively of oxadiazole moiety); δ (DMSO- d_6) 8.37–7.5 (14H, m, ArH); m/z (rel. intensity %) R = m-chlorophenyl, 396 (M^+ , 100), 305 (12), 245 (49), 199 (56), 163 (10), 136 (36) and 125 (10).

Similarly, other acids were synthesised (Table 1).

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Synthesis and Fungitoxicity of some 5-Arylamino-2-polynitroarylthio-1,3,4- thiadiazoles

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1,3,4-Thiadiazoles are reported to exhibit broad spectrum of biological properties¹. Thiol group is an important toxophoric group especially active against fungi². The presence of SH group in the thiadiazole nucleus imparts fungitoxicity to these compounds³. A literature survey on 5-arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazole-2-thiols (1) led to the fact that the polynitroarylthio derivatives of this heterocyclic moiety have not been explored for their fungitoxicity. It is well-known that polynitroaryl sulphides possess stronger antifungal properties than the parent mercapto compounds. On the basis of these observations, it was thought of interest to prepare a large number of polynitroarylthio derivatives of 5-arylamino-2-mercapto-1,3,4-thiadiazoles

having halogen, nitro, methyl, methoxy, ethoxy groups at different positions in the 5-phenylamino nucleus with a view to test their antifungal properties and to establish a structure-activity relationship.

5-Arylamino-2-polynitroarylthio-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (2) have been prepared by the condensation between halogenonitrobenzenes and 5-arylamino-2-mercapto-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (1) in ethanolic solution in the presence of NaOH.

1; R¹ = aryl, R² = H

2; R¹ = aryl, R² = 2,4-dinitrophenyl, 2,4,6-trinitrophenyl, 3-chloro-4,6-dinitrophenyl

Thus, three halogenonitrobenzenes have been condensed with nine 5-arylamino-2-mercapto-1,3,4-thiadiazoles to give the corresponding 5-arylamino-2-polynitrophenylthio-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (Table 1). The ir spectra of these 5-substituted-arylamino-2-polynitroarylthio-1,3,4-thiadiazoles agree with their structures. 5-Arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazole-5-thiol showed the characteristic ir bands at 3 300 (NH), 2 600 (SH), 715 (C-S), 1 600 (C=N) and 815, 735 cm⁻¹ (substituted-phenyl). These bands are common in these compounds. The band due to thiol disappeared, in addition, in the polynitrophenylthio derivatives strong absorption peaks due

TABLE 1—5-ARYLAMINO-2-POLYNITROARYLTHIO-1,3,4-THIADIAZOLE (2)*

Sl. no.	R ¹	R ^{2,3}	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	% inhibition (1 : 10000)		
						<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>P. exigua</i>
1.	Phenyl	(a)	255	95	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂	65.0	75.0	55.5
2.	Benzyl	(a)	175	98	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂	77.1	81.7	60.4
3.	<i>p</i> -Phenetyl	(a)	215	89	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂	61.7	66.6	48.2
4.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	(a)	200	97	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₄ S ₂	59.8	65.2	47.8
5.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	(a)	199	85	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₃ O ₂ ClS ₂	50.9	57.9	53.5
6.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	(a)	177	90	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₄ S ₂	57.7	60.6	54.8
7.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	(a)	191	89	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂	59.2	61.1	55.4
8.	5-Chloro- <i>o</i> -tolyl	(a)	185	75	C ₁₄ H ₉ ClN ₃ O ₂ S ₂	61.7	60.8	62.7
9.	5-Nitro- <i>o</i> -tolyl	(a)	140	70	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂	51.8	47.5	55.4
10.	Phenyl	(b)	239	81	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₃ O ₄ S ₂	67.1	78.2	56.1
11.	Benzyl	(b)	168	75	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₃ O ₄ S ₂	79.3	89.3	62.9
12.	<i>p</i> -Phenetyl	(b)	220	89	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₄ S ₂	63.0	68.1	55.3
13.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	(b)	184	94	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₆ S ₂	62.4	67.1	49.3
14.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	(b)	210	92	C ₁₄ H ₇ N ₃ O ₄ ClS ₂	58.1	59.6	53.8
15.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	(b)	180	83	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₃ O ₆ S ₂	58.1	62.5	55.7
16.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	(b)	215	70	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₃ O ₄ S ₂	60.0	64.2	57.6
17.	5-Chloro- <i>o</i> -tolyl	(b)	191	75	C ₁₄ H ₉ ClN ₃ O ₄ S ₂	63.8	58.4	64.9
18.	5-Nitro- <i>o</i> -tolyl	(b)	155	89	C ₁₅ H ₉ N ₄ O ₆ S ₂	47.3	44.6	51.3
19.	Phenyl	(c)	154	77	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₃ O ₄ ClS ₂	61.1	70.8	54.7
20.	Benzyl	(c)	177	81	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₃ O ₄ ClS ₂	71.9	76.4	59.1
21.	<i>p</i> -Phenetyl	(c)	188	85	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₄ ClS ₂	51.7	63.2	48.3
22.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	(c)	197	93	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₆ ClS ₂	58.3	64.1	46.7
23.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	(c)	165	86	C ₁₄ H ₇ N ₃ O ₄ Cl ₂ S ₂	45.5	55.5	51.3
24.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	(c)	171	90	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₃ O ₆ ClS ₂	56.6	61.4	54.9
25.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	(c)	185	89	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₃ O ₄ ClS ₂	58.7	63.2	55.9
26.	5-Chloro- <i>o</i> -tolyl	(c)	215	79	C ₁₄ H ₉ ClN ₃ O ₄ Cl ₂ S ₂	61.7	56.8	61.7
27.	5-Nitro- <i>o</i> -tolyl	(c)	195	88	C ₁₅ H ₉ N ₄ O ₆ ClS ₂	46.8	42.9	50.7

* Satisfactory N and S analyses obtained for all the compounds.

** (a) = 2,4-Dinitrophenyl, (b) = 2,4,6-trinitrophenyl, (c) = 3-chloro-4,6-dinitrophenyl.